

Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies

25/4 Oct-Dec 2021, ISSN P-0972-3331 | E-2582-8711 | **92-103**

www.punejournal.in | DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5117983

Stable URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5117983>

Jesus and Ambedkar: The Relevance of the Emancipatory Correlation between Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar to the Contemporary Indian Catholic Church

G. Arokia Sebastin Babu, HGN
Research Scholar, Jnana Deepa, Pune

Abstract: Being built on the values like, justice, equality, liberty and fraternity, the preamble of Indian Constitution, the existing caste-based divisive situation in India, is worrisome. Obviously, constant effort has been taken to undo the caste discriminative factors at various times, by different individuals. Among those individuals, Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar stands unique. Being born in the same oppressive situation, he deeply analyzed the caste system, vigorously fought this systemic evil, organized people, initiated its systematic eradication and tirelessly worked for justice and equity. His sacrifice is not exclusively for Dalits, but to all who are oppressed, neglected, discriminated, and exploited. Thereby Dr. Ambedkar becomes a universal icon to

Cite as: Babu, G. Arokia Sebastin. (2021). Jesus and Ambedkar: The Relevance of an Emancipatory Correlation between Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar to the Contemporary Indian Catholic Church (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, Oct-Dec 2021(25/4), **92-103**. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5117983>.

fight injustice and inequality. Deeply impressed by this great human being, I find those values of Dr. Ambedkar are nothing but the Kingdom values, preached and lived by Jesus. In Christian sense, I would say that God instrumented Dr. Ambedkar to realize His Kingdom values in our times. Truly, this accommodative understanding would help us to get inspired by the prophetic role of Dr. Ambedkar and work for the emancipation of the oppressed in our localities.

Keywords: Jesus, Dr. Ambedkar, Dalits, India, Caste, Oppression, Liberation

Introduction

India is well known for her rich heritage, variety of cultures, religious traditions, languages, and ethnicities. Though she contains such diversities within herself, proudly she stands unique for her nature ‘unity in diversity’. The projection of her shores displays a glorious side of Indianness. But when we walk through the streets of India, her divisive and discriminative face which is so cruel and inhuman to the core glares at us. The prime factor for it is the caste system founded on graded inequality. It is an inbuilt ideology that exists in every Indian’s mind and heart. It is predestined for an Indian to be born in a particular caste. Naturally the people at the lowest layer of the system (depressed class or Dalits) are the victims of this unjust structure. It is in this oppressive scenario, Christianity landed in Indian soil. The Dalits who were longing for equality, liberty and fraternity embraced Christianity with the hope of attaining those values. Unfortunately, Christianity in India also adopted the caste practices. In the salvation history, God has picked up prophets like Moses, Isaiah, Jeramiah, and others in order to set free His people from the legal, social, or political restraints or bondages. Finally, He sent His Son Jesus, the Prophet of the prophets, to set His people free. Today, God raises human beings ‘to act in the manner of prophets’ and to emancipate His people in their own respective continents and nations. Likewise, God raised Dr. Ambedkar in India to act as a prophet in order to set free His

oppressed people from the socio-political-economic slavery of India. Building an emancipatory correlation between Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar is an invitation extended to the Indian Catholic Church to emancipate the Dalits in India.

Social Hierarchy Based On Caste: An Oppressive Structure of Indian Society

India's caste system is possibly the world's longest surviving social hierarchy. It encompasses a complex order of social groups on the basis of ritual purity. In Indian context, the Hindu *Varna* system divides whole society and places *Brahmins* at the top, followed by *Kshatriyas* or warriors, *Vaishyas* or traders, and *Sudras* or servants. The Dalits are considered unworthy to be in the hierarchical status of the caste system. As the caste system is religiously underpinned, it is fiercely advocated as one of the religious practices (Srinivas, 1969: 265). Not only Hindus but also other religious communities practice caste though they may theoretically reject it (Thapar, 2004: 67). The repercussions of inhuman caste practices are oppression, economic exploitation, and social exclusion. The Caste system, by its nature, poses a threat to equality, human dignity, human rights and social justice which jointly form a human community of peace and harmony. Anything that corrodes equality, dignity, rights and justice, is undoubtedly evil.

Jesus' Encounter with His Oppressive Society

The oppressive picture of India resembles the oppressive nature of the Jewish community at the time of Jesus. Being incarnated in time and space, Jesus encountered all societal oppressive realities and challenged any structure that promoted inequality, discrimination, oppression, and repression. Thus Jesus becomes a forerunner in liberating the oppressed people of any structure.

Similarities between Jewish Society and Indian Society

Though Indian caste discrimination and Jewish racial discrimination have their origin of discrimination and inequality in purity-pollution ideology, both differ essentially. Jewish racial discrimination labels someone as untouchable by way of his/her act or physical stature that comes from biological inter-mingling of two races. On the contrary, Indian caste discrimination labels someone as untouchable by birth. Even if two individuals appear to be similar in their physical and intellectual qualities, since one is born in a particular caste, s/he is considered to be impure and untouchable. In both the cases, religion perpetuates discrimination and sustains oppression. Basically both the systems value inequality, injustice, discrimination, and oppression and distort human dignity. The victims cry in hopelessness, lifelessness, and desperation. It is they who long for liberation.

Social Stance of Jesus

Jesus' social stance gives a radical message to his community by emphasizing on regaining justice prophetically. In his first appearance in his hometown synagogue, he reads the prophet Isaiah's revolutionary call for justice and liberation for the poor (Lk 4:16-21). A carpenter's son reclaims the dream of justice. This dream contains liberty to captives, recovery of sight to the blind and freedom to the oppressed. Jesus establishes God's reign of justice here and now. He sides with the weak and confronts the powerful. His mission is defined by justice and irrupts into human history with all its structures.

Jesus' Liberative Vision and Mission

Abba Experience

Anyone who works for the liberation of the oppressed and marginalized experiences *Abba*. The traditional understanding of *Abba* experience has direct reference to the intimacy of Jesus with

the Father. But here we underscore the suffering of Jesus on account of the abandonment of the Father on the cross where he cried “My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?” (Mk 15:34) and “It is finished” (Jn 19:30). It is the *Abba* experience of the detachment from the Father. Soares-Prabhu argues that ‘*Abba*’ is a heart that goes out to the poor and oppressed (Soares-Prabhu, 2003: 4). The vision of the kingdom of God originates from the *Abba* experience that assures freedom, fellowship and justice (Soares-Prabhu, 2003: 51). Jesus’ life is an experience that expressed itself in an almost exclusive commitment to the liberation of those who suffered discrimination in any way. Thus a commitment to work for the liberation of discriminated people is an outcome of *Abba* experience and it is a free gift of God that anybody can receive irrespective of any barrier.

Human Response

Abba experience necessarily pushes anyone to respond instantly. It is a response against the forces opposed to God’s reign of justice, equality, peace and harmony. Kappen says that the reign of God is embodied in things, events, persons and experiences that lie at the root of humans’ response (Kappen, 1977: 62). The purpose of God in human history has to be realized through human effort for the liberation of all. Thus *Abba* experience is manifested in Jesus’ liberative endeavors in which everyone is invited to participate.

Preferential Option for the Marginalized

Liberative endeavours are rooted on the preferential option for the marginalized or priorities one sets in favour of the victims. This option expresses itself in concrete actions. Jesus took an irreversible stand for the marginalized that no pressure of the public opinion could ever discourage him (Jn 8:1-10), nor the violence of the established authority could frighten him (Lk 13:31-33). And he passionately executed his option by breaking the Sabbath (Mk 2:23-3:6), ignoring the rules of the ritual cleanliness (Mk 7:1-15),

touching the lepers (Mk 1:41), and dining with the socially outcasts, tax collectors and sinners (Mk 2:15-17; Lk 15:1-2) Therefore, the preferential option for the marginalized is a firm stand that challenges any oppressive and unjust structure or institution. Anyone who truly follows Jesus, chooses this option uncompromisingly.

Realization of the Kingdom of God

In fact, the preferential option for the marginalized is the beginning of the realization of the kingdom of God. For Jesus, the kingdom of God entails the overcoming of misery and the transformation of society for the sake of the poor. Realizing the kingdom of God is working for the liberation of the poor from unjust structures. Leonardo Boff says that the kingdom of God is a complete, global and structural transfiguration and the revolution of the reality of human beings (Boff, 1978: 53). Hence, anyone who works for the liberation of the poor, the marginalized and the oppressed, ultimately works for the realization of the kingdom of God.

Hope for an Ultimate Liberation

The realization of the kingdom includes both the present and the future. It is an on-going process that continues today, tomorrow and forever in various forms by different persons. Kappan says that one can understand the kingdom which has an already and not yet character. Understanding this eschatological nature of the kingdom, Jesus focuses on the future of human community, an absolute future, free from every possibility of alienation. Gutierrez argues that the prophets had on the one hand their orientation towards future and on the other, their concern with the present. Fighting in the present for a better present and future is a prophetic call.

Mahatma Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar: The Indian Prophet of the Oppressed

God, the liberator, raised Mahatma Dr. Ambedkar in India ‘to act as a prophet’ in order to set free His oppressed people from the socio-political-economic-spiritual slavery of India (I find it more fitting to attribute the title ‘Mahatma’ to Dr. Ambedkar who extraordinarily worked for the emancipation of Dalits). In the context of Religious Pluralistic India, my attempt is not Christianizing Dr. Ambedkar, rather finding the liberative kingdom elements in him in order to arrive at pathways for the Indian Catholic Church to fight against Indian social evils.

Untouchable Experience: The Abba Experience of Dr. Ambedkar for a Prophetic Realization

Every experience of Dr. Ambedkar was an *Abba* experience (the suffering of a complete detachment like that of a Calvary experience) that convinced him to form himself as a liberator of the Dalits and such experiences were heart-breaking, inhuman and cruel. Beginning from his early age till his death, even after his death, he has been experiencing the untouchability. The chain of *Abba* experiences of Dr. Ambedkar amidst his people and in his life made him to realize the need for a liberative and prophetic mission for his people. It was a self-realization of a prophet.

Dr. Ambedkar’s Response to Abba Experience

As a response to his *Abba* experience of inhuman treatment of untouchability, Dr. Ambedkar internally felt the need of an intellectual weapon to encounter the institutionalized discriminatory structure. Thereby he grabbed all the opportunities to equip himself with the sole aim of fighting against caste discrimination and untouchability. One can intuitively understand how God works through different individuals to shape His chosen ones for a great mission.

Preferential Option for the Oppressed

The *Abba* experience of a person results in taking a stand for the poor, oppressed and the marginalized. It is undoubtedly true with Dr. Ambedkar also. Once he said, “Whenever there has been a conflict between my personal interests and the interests of the country as a whole, I have always placed the claim of the country above my personal claims... Whenever there is conflict of interest between the country and Untouchables so far as I am concerned Untouchables’ interests will take precedence over the interests of the country.” Through this he strongly advocated that India must assure equal status to all classes in religious, social, economic and political matters.

Realization of the Kingdom of God

Dr. Ambedkar placing himself at the forefront marched forward to work for the emancipation of the Dalits in India by way of the realization of Justice, Equality, Liberty and Fraternity. He walked like Moses in leading the people from slavery. He became the spokesperson of the oppressed people like any other prophets in the salvation history. Ultimately we can find him as a Kingdom Realizer. Dr. Ambedkar used the *Constitution of India* as a powerful weapon to demolish the caste-based oppressive structures and to realize the kingdom values in India.

Prophetic Hope for the Future

Dr. Ambedkar functioned as a Prophet having a great hope for the liberative future of Dalits. He awakened hope for an ultimate liberation in the hearts of the Dalits and in all those who worked for the emancipation of Dalits. His humility and unexpected entry into the Constituent Assembly definitely portrays God’s hand in his election which he had never thought of. His desire to safeguard the interests of the Scheduled Castes exhibits God’s plan for the liberation and emancipation of the oppressed people. Cumulatively they speak of God’s plan to instil a hope and liberation in the hearts

and minds of the discriminated, through Dr. Ambedkar, His chosen prophet.

Dr. Ambedkar's Just Society: The Kingdom of God

In Hindu social order, there is no room for individual justice. Dr. Ambedkar says that in his just society, caste has no place. For him justice is simply another name for liberty, equality and fraternity. This leads one to reject completely the old life before entering into new life. However, this transformation does not take place in a day or two. It is a process or a journey towards its completion. Obviously this journey gives everyone a hope for an ultimate liberation – complete liberation. It is with this hope Dr. Ambedkar laboured throughout his life for the emancipation of the Dalits. He also has set a platform for anyone who works for the same cause.

Relevance of Dr. Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar to the Indian Catholic Church

Dr. Ambedkar, having been experienced Christianity in foreign countries, sharply critiqued the unsocial attitude of the Christian missionaries; the Indian Christian community as a disjointed community; high class nature; and the treatment of caste Christians over the Dalit Christians. It is true even with today's Christianity.

The social teachings of the Church insist on equality, liberty and fraternity through *Humanae Vitae*, *Gaudium et Spes*, *Populorum Progressio*, *Dignitatis Humanae*, *Evangelium Vitae*, *Querida Amazonia*.

Critical Evaluation of the Indian Catholic Church

Dr. Ambedkar was able to feel the pain of the Dalits because he was one of the victims of the inhuman and discriminatory caste practices. To have *Abba* experience, one needs to incarnate oneself and become an insider, perhaps only then it becomes an *Abba* experience for the particular individual. But the Indian Catholic

Church has not yet incarnated into the Dalitness. She looks at the Dalit issues as an outsider. As an outsider she would not be able to understand the suffering of discrimination. Undoubtedly, she keeps herself away deliberately.

Once Dr. Ambedkar had the *Abba* experience amidst caste discriminative practices and customs, he responded convincingly by way of working for a casteless society in order to protect his fellow human beings from untouchability, discrimination and oppression. Since the Indian Catholic Church does not have a radical incarnation and *Abba* experience, she is incapable of going against the well-established oppressive structures of the caste system. Very sadly she has incorporated the system within herself. Pathetically, she had never taken wholeheartedly any lawful measure on the field to eradicate caste system within her boundaries in order to promote equality.

Dr. Ambedkar chose always the right path which keeps the depressed class in the forefront. He never compromised his values with anything or anybody. He fought against even Gandhi the most respected figure of his time and placed the depressed class ahead of national interest. He raised his voice against all the unjust structures. But the Indian Catholic Church keeps silence whenever it is possible and especially when justice is denied at the cost of the poor Dalits.

Dr. Ambedkar certainly awakened hope for ultimate liberation of the oppressed of this country. He never wanted the depressed people to live at the mercy of the oppressors, rather he encouraged them to fight and claim their rights. Truly speaking, does the Indian Catholic Church give hope? If she gives hope, to whom does she give?

Need of Dr. Ambedkars in the Church

The Catholic Church lives today in the same situation in which Dr. Ambedkar lived prophetically. He has taken a lead in the liberating prophetic mission for Dalits in his time. The condition of the Dalits

implicitly remains same even today. Though there are number of individuals who work for the liberation of the Dalits within the Church, their effects are never brought into limelight. The Church in India needs Dr. Ambedkars to take up the same prophetic mission in our time to abolish discriminative caste practices. The mission could be successful only when the interest of the Dalits is placed above our personal interests. This is the realization of the kingdom of God in India.

Conclusion

Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar cannot be certainly weighed on the same balance. But both Jesus and Dr. Ambedkar, within their respective historical context, have done the primary and preliminary ground work for a constant fight in order to have liberation which gives the foretaste of the ultimate liberation. This constant fight against oppression has got diluted in today's Indian Catholic Church or perhaps she has even well accommodated the oppressive elements at various convenient levels. We realize that the Catholic Church, which is situated in the same social scenario, distances herself from embracing Jesus' model of radical commitment to address the issues related to oppression. Or oftentimes she washes her hand with charity works which in no way seem to emancipate the Dalits. The Indian Catholic Church must understand 'what the Dalits need is not charity but justice'.

References

- Ambedkar, B. R. (1936). *Annihilation of Caste*. New Delhi: Navayana.
- Beteille, Andre. (1969). *Castes: Old and New*. Bombay: Asia Publishing House.
- Boff, Leonardo. (1978). *Jesus Christ Liberator: A Critical Christology for Our Time*, trans. Patrick Hughes. New York: Orbis Books.
- Dumont, Louis. (1970). *Homo Hierarchicus*. Translated by Mark Sainbury. Delhi: Vikas Publications.

- Jaffrelot, Christopher. (2005). *Analysing and Fighting Caste: Dr Ambedkar and Untouchability*. Delhi: Permanent Black.
- Kappen, Sebastian. (1977). *Jesus and Freedom*. New York: Orbis Books.
- Massey, James. (2003). *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar: A Study in Just Society*. New Delhi: Centre for Dalit/Subaltern Studies.
- Meier, John P. (2001). *A Marginal Jew: Rethinking the Historical Jew*. Vol. 3. New York: Doubleday.
- Soares-Prabhu, George M. (2003). *The Dharma of Jesus*. Edited by Francis Xavier D'Sa. New York: Orbis Books.
- Sobrinho, Jon. (1978). *Christology at the Crossroads: A Latin American Approach*. Translated by John Drury. New York: Orbis Books.
- Srinivas, M. N. (1969). "The Caste System in India." In *Social Inequality*, edited by Andre Beteille, 265-272. Middlesex: Penguin Books.
- Thapar, Romila. (2004). *Early India: From the Origins to AD 1300*. Los Angeles: University of California Press.

G. Arokia Sebastin Babu HGN, is a research scholar in JD, Pune and working as a lecturer in the Department of Theology, St. Joseph's Major Seminary, Khammam, Telengana. He has authored a book in Tamil and written few articles. Email: asbabuji19@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0001-7671-2053.

Article received: March 28, 2021
Accepted: July 4, 2021
Word count: 3210

© by the authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).